

From Darkness to Light: Speculation on The Life of An Unborn Baby Inside the Mother's Womb with Reference to *What Becomes Us* by Micah Perks

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The World has seen different domains of the Literature in every one of these years. It has never neglected to acknowledge the people, through its different domains on human development. Ian Micah Perks takes one such job and he prophesizes the life in the dark world womb, through his novels. He places the light into the womb and picturises life of unborn in this novel. Human beings are conceived as 'blank slates', since the learning process starts in the womb, they are coming in these created in this world with their very own set of memories and Character. In *What Becomes Us*, a nine months old unborn narrator learn out about this outside world through his external society, even before he come into it, through his auditory sensory mechanisms. This article makes an attempt to study the psychological development of the character of the unborn baby and how the effect of Psycho- social changes influences the unborn baby.

The unborn narrator is aware in his mother's womb, everything began like an explosion and all of a sudden, he was pulled into this world with the series of consciousness, as an detective observer. He is clever understanding about both external and internal self. Since, the human character is planned in the womb dependent on the environmental and maternal components, it is obviously true for this situation of the unborn. The narrator expresses the, Human 'consciousness' differs from 'conscience', while the first one is awareness, the other is ethical judgment. Thus, awareness starts even before one's birth to the world, however conscience comes just through one's experience. That is the reason the unborn baby needs ethical judgements of good and bad, due to the lack of his experience and empathy.

The path of consciousness prompts learning about one's own self, parents, external environment and outer society. It makes the unborn to adjust to outer environment and situation. As per the geneticists, each human mind is a 'blank slate' at the time of conception; things are infused as one grows. Unborn are learning out about their outer world with the assistance of their tangible auditory and sensory components, scientists are looking this as the survival technique of the unborn in this present world, "We confess that when mother first saw us on the ultrasound, she was a little taken aback" (W.B.U, p.9). These lines of the unborn narrator, clarifies his source of learning. Listening is the strong source of learning in the womb, the repetition of sounds is acclimatized in their brain in an unconscious manner. the unborn narrator says,

Mother is an agnostic, but we know the three of us are now alone. We don't have delusions of grandeur, we don't expect God, if there is a God, to intervene in our tiny drama, but still, we know someone is out there, listening, perhaps deciding our fate. (W.B.U, p. 8)

The unborn narrator's life is in clear stress, where his mother is intending to kill the unborn narrator's father John, with her brother in law, with whom she has illicit relationship. This creates confusion in the psyche of the unborn, and gives him bad impression about this world. The world which is depicted before him is extraordinarily little, with a couple of individuals from his family and all that he knows is simply news, which is an illusionary one. With these information's and learning, he envisions this present world through his psychological cognition and turns out with a negative perception.

The negative thoughts of the Pregnant mother leads to the anxiety, stress, fear and trauma, where both the mother and the unborn are associated with each other and they share their blood, food, thoughts and destiny together. In what Becomes us the creator expresses that, "Three minutes without her and our hearts would stop." (W.B.U, p.8). Their lives are inter-twined, each shares the same soul but the mind is two. One lives within the other, and are bounded together, listening the thoughts, working like a conscience at times. The eating habits of the mother enriches for the development of the baby, the junk food like alcohol which she takes creates poor physical and intellectual impacts lower his senses of awareness.

The maternal attachment is certain, and despite the fact that a mother is cruel to others, she is good to her baby constantly. It is due to the mental attachment of the mother and the child. The narrator in What Becomes Us tells that, "Because that is the moment we came to consciousness in an explosion of bright, bright blue" (W.B.U, p.3). The father's affection is taken away by way of the satanic intentions of his mother Trudy, the destiny of the unborn narrator is absolutely shattered, it results in psychological stress and the impacts of these incidents affects the psychological stress and cognitive development of the unborn inside the womb.

Most commonly every individual fails to recognize the presence of the unborn while they are within the womb. They fail to understand that the domestic violence and the unpleasant mental notions of mother at once affects the unborn, the unborn narrator in this novel is a paragon of this case. Thus, one has to realize that even the unborn infants are motivated by way of their external surroundings, even though they are now not physically present there. On the whole, the unborn are also need be pampered with more care to create a pleasant environment, which contributes for the well-described prenatal experience and future.

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